

Real-Time Traffic Sign Recognition based AI Edge computing

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Abstract—Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a model used in many disciplines to classify objects in video streaming, clustering, pattern recognition, and prediction. With many systems that deal with the classification problem, mobility is often necessary. In this article, an implementation of Tiny-YOLOv3 (You Only Look Once) with CNN in Internet of Things (IoT) devices is proposed to address the traffic sign classification problem on the EDGE AI Sipeed MAIX platform. The main feature of this module is the availability of the first RISC-V 64 AI module with K210-KPU inside, allowing high performance with low power consumption. The proposed method uses the K-Means algorithm to group our training set and find other boxes of apparently excellent targets. The performances of the proposed work are evaluated against the BTSD (Belgium Traffic Sign Detection) dataset and the experiments show that the proposed approach achieves an excellent compromise between speed and precision. The system performs the detection recognition process in approximately 112ms for each frame in (KPU) and 9 FPS in the video stream.

Index Terms—Deep learning, Edge accelerator, Edge computing, IOT, Tiny-YOLOv3, Traffic Sign Recognition, Edge AI, Sipeed MAIX.

I. INTRODUCTION

The recognition of traffic signs has received considerable research interest over several decades due to its challenging nature as a computer vision problem. As part of Advanced Driving Assistance Systems (ADAS), Traffic Sign Recognition (TSR) systems play an important role in improving car safety and guiding information to drivers [1]. However, many factors make the detection and recognition tasks difficult, such as lighting changes, poor image quality due to low resolution, bad weather conditions, partial occlusions, color distortion, motion blur, etc (See Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Examples for difficulties facing the Traffic Sign Recognition task

In recent years, there has been immense interest in classifying video streaming objects using deep learning (DL). With the development of graphics processing units (GPUs) supporting high computational complexity, DL has become increasingly common in object detection and image recognition. In particular, deep convolutional neural networks (CNN) are the dominant approach to identify patterns in images and video [2], as they provide faster speed and higher accuracy compared to the traditional methods. For this purpose, CNN-based methods can be divided into region-based techniques and regression-based techniques. The region-based convolution neural networks (R-CNN) aim to propose the regions and then classify them. They offer superior performance in terms of localization and classification accuracy; however, they produce a high cost in terms of memory and latency [3]. Therefore, Fast-RCNN and Faster R-CNN were introduced to improve the speed and achieve greater precision [4]. These approaches have shown superior performance in terms of location and classification accuracy and turn out to be a very promising tool, especially for real-time performance in the TSR system [5]. However, these detectors cannot detect small objects, which is essential for recognizing traffic signs.

The regression-based single networks (e.g., YOLO (You Only Look Once) [6], SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) [7] rely on a single convolutional network to perform bounding box prediction and class probabilities at the same time from an input image. In [8], the You Only Look Once (YOLO) approach combined the classification and localization tasks in a single convolutional network and directly performs regression to detect targets in the image. The improved versions of YOLO, YOLOv2 and YOLOv3 have shown promising results regarding the accuracy and speed required for object detection problems [9].

Taking advantage of the significant computing capacity of the GPU to accelerate the DL in the inference phase, as well as in the learning phase. In addition, these on-board systems are severely limited due to power consumption requirements.

In this work, we propose an implementation of the

convolutional neural network Tiny-YOLOv3 to address the traffic sign classification problem in the EDGE AI Sipeed MAIX platform. The main feature of this module is the availability of the 1st RISC-V 64 AI Module that includes K210 KPU inside, which enables high performance computing with low power consumption. The implemented algorithm makes it possible to deal with the problem of the classification of traffic signs in a continuous video stream with reasonable accuracy and speed. The proposed method uses the K-means algorithm to group our training set to find more excellent prior frames of the objectives. The results of the proposed approach are evaluated in the Belgian Traffic Sign Detection Data Set (BTSD). Experiments show that the proposed method achieves an excellent balance between speed and precision. The system executes the detection / recognition process in approximately 112 ms for each image in (KPU) and 9 FPS in video stream.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the framework of the proposed work. Experimental results are presented and discussed in section 3. Finally, section 4 concludes the article.

II. METHODOLOGY AND FRAMEWORK

A. Problem statement

We are implementing a deep CNN model based on Tiny-YOLOv3 on the EDGE AI Sipeed MAIX platform to solve the detection problem on the Belgium Traffic Sign dataset. The objective is to obtain a model which will be able to simultaneously detect and classify traffic signs. The proposed method uses the K-means algorithm to group our training set in order to find more excellent target boxes.

B. YOLOv3

The YOLOv3 [9] network is an evolution of the YOLO [8] and YOLOv2 [10] networks. Compared to the Faster R-CNN network, the YOLO network transforms the detection problem into a regression problem. It does not require a proxy region and generates the bounding box coordinates and probabilities for each class directly through regression. This greatly increases the detection speed compared to Faster R-CNN. The YOLO detection model is shown in Figure 2. The network divides each image in the training set into $S \times S$ grids. If the center of truth of the target terrain falls on a grid, then the grid is responsible for detecting the objective. Each grid predicts the bounding boxes B and their confidence scores, as well as the class C conditional probabilities.

Confidence is defined as follows:

Confidence =

$$P_r(object) * IoU_{pred}^{truth}; P_r(object) \in \{0; 1\}$$

If we have the target on the grid, $P_r(object) = 1$ and 0 otherwise. IoU_{pred} true is used to determine the correspondence between the reference and the predicted bounding box. Confidence shows whether the grid contains objects and the precision of the bounding box expected when it contains

objects. In the event that several bounding boxes detect the same target, the No Maximum Suppression (NMS) method is used by YOLO to determine the best bounding box. Although YOLO offers a higher speed compared to Faster RCNN, it has the disadvantage of having a large detection error. To solve this problem, YOLOv2 presents the idea of the anchor box in Faster R-CNN and also uses the k-means clustering method to reproduce a priori appropriate bounding boxes. Therefore, the number of anchor boxes required to achieve the same intersection-on-join (IoU) results is reduced. YOLOv2 improves the structure of the network and uses a convolutional layer to replace the fully connected layer in the output layer of YOLO. YOLOv2 also offers batch normalization, high resolution classifier, dimension groups, direct location prediction, detailed functionality, multi-scale training and other approaches to greatly improve detection accuracy over YOLO. In [11] an incremental version of YOLO is introduced, called YOLOv3, with faster detection time and better detection accuracy. In our study, we focus on real-time detection with

Fig. 2. Basic calculations in the YOLO Algorithm

a limited hardware condition that accommodates embedded systems. Therefore, we use the Tiny version of the YOLOv3 algorithm. This version has 13 convolutional layers followed by multiple subsampling layers to extract features from the image.

C. Tiny-YOLOv3

The basic structure of Tiny-YOLOv3 contains only seven convolutional layers, in other words, it has a reduced number of convolutional layers. Features are extracted based on a small number of 1×1 and 3×3 convolutional layers. Tiny-YOLOv3 also uses the grouping layer instead of the YOLOv3 convolutional layer with a step size of 2 to have a reduced dimension, which means that Tiny-YOLOv3 has a significant improvement over other previous versions, namely the ability to perform detection at three different scales. It can also predict more bounding boxes than before. Therefore, this method does not need to use a large amount of memory, which greatly reduces the need for hardware. The Tiny-YOLOv3 process is shown in Figure 3.

D. Sipeed MAIX: AI at the edge

In this work, we implemented the solution using the SiPEED MAiX AI board, shown in Figure 4. The specifications of the

Fig. 3. The network structure of Tiny-YOLOv3

board are shown in Table I. This platform contains an on-board device with hardware acceleration of intelligence (AI). MAiX is the module explicitly developed for SiPEED and designed to run AI at the edge [12]. It provides high performance considering a small physical and energy surface which allow the implementation of a high precision AI and a competitive price.

Fig. 4. The Sipeed MAIX-I module

Among the advantages of this device:

- A complete infrastructure composed of hardware and software to facilitate the deployment and implementation of AI-based solutions;
- high performance, low power consumption and also low cost, which enables wide deployment of high quality AI on board;
- It can be used for a variety of industrial use cases, such as predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, machine vision, robotics, voice recognition, etc.

TABLE I
SOME PERFORMANCE NUMBERS OF THE BOARD

Parameter	Specifications
CPU	64-bit RISC-v processor and core
Chipset	K210 - RISC - V
Image Recognition	qvq at 60fps / vg at 30fps
Clock (GHz)	0.40
AI resources	KPU
OS/Language	uPython
Dimensions (mm)	60x43x5

E. Framework

In this work, it was decided to use the TensorFlow DL framework for the implementation. It is an open source software library basically developed by Google for numerical computation based on data flowcharts. A chart is a data structure that presents the entire calculation to be performed. To this end, mathematical operations are described by nodes, and edges represent the data transferred between nodes. The data in TensorFlow is described in the form of tensors. The tensor is therefore an n-dimensional array responding to a particular transformation law. It describes an object placed in a specific coordinate system. When there is a change in the coordinate systems, the inputs of a tensor also transform in this way, so that the tensor always presents the same map in the new coordinate system. YOLO training demands a powerful graphics processing unit (GPU), it is in this context, the experiments were carried out on an Intel (R) Xeon (R) E5-1620 @ 3.60 Ghz processor using NVIDIA GTX 1050 graphics processor Ti.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Traffic sign recognition involves two main tasks: Detect the traffic signs within the images and then classify the detected signs. In this work, we propose a model to recognize Belgian traffic signs based on the Tiny-YOLOV3 algorithm implemented in the embedded platform for edge computing Sipeed MAIX-I, as well as analyze the performance of the inference. We also used the k-means clustering algorithm to identify the size of the anchors, one of the important hyper parameters of the Tiny-YOLOV3 algorithm. In (Figure 5) a flow diagram of the proposed system is presented.

Fig. 5. Flow chart of the proposed method

A. Dataset

We are exploiting the BTSD (Belgium Traffic Sign Detection) dataset [13] to train and evaluate the detection and classification purposes. It contains 62 different classes of traffic signs and there are 13 main categories: undefined, other, triangles, red circles, blue circles, red-blue circles, diamonds,

yield, stop, forbidden, squares, rectangles upwards, rectangles downwards.

The dataset was generated by taking images from multiple angles in urban street scenes. The number of training, validation and test images was 5905, 1301 and 1750, respectively. These images can have multiple traffic signs or even no traffic signs. It can be observed that these traffic signs occupy a small part of the image and are recorded under various constrained conditions (variations in lighting, orientation, occlusions, etc) as presented in Figure 6. The BTSD annotations provide labels and their corresponding bounding boxes Elements: x-coordinate, y-coordinate, width and height as well as the class of traffic signs.

Fig. 6. Examples for difficulties facing the traffic sign recognition on the BTSD database

B. Experiment results

In this work, we performed an implementation of Tiny YOLOv3 on the MAIX AI platform at the edge, which is the cheapest AI accelerator on the market. To deal with the traffic sign classification problem, the Belgian Traffic Sign Benchmark [13] dataset is used. Neural network training lasted over 24 hours with Intel Core Xeon E5-1260 and NVDIIA GeForce GTX 1050ti processors. Over 10,000 iterations have been performed, which is quite satisfactory for this recognition task.

Tables II and III show the energy efficiency of Tiny-YOLOV3 implemented on the KPU system integrated in AI Accelerator on a PC with GPU NVDIIA GeForce GTX 1050ti, Google Cloud TPU and CPU Xeon (R) E5-1620 technologies. To convert the tflite model to a k model supported by the k210 AI accelerator used in MAIX AI, we used the nncase multiplatform toolkit for multiplatform neural network optimization for fast inference [12]. To train our model, we use the Darknet neural network framework using this parameter 'batch = 24', which means, we used 24 images for each training step. If "subdivisions = 8", the batch is therefore divided by 8 to reduce the GPU requirements. "Classes = 5" (this value indicates the number of object

classes for which we have 5 categories of traffic signs) and finally Filter = (Classes + 5) × 3 in our case "Filter = 30".

TABLE II
RESULTS OF THE TINY-YOLO'S v3 WORK (1)

	MAIX AI	NVDIIA GeForce GTX 1050ti
Recognition time (R=1280x720) per (s)	1.3	0.012
FPS (320 × 240)	9.2	57.4
Power Consumption (W)	0.5	75

TABLE III
RESULTS OF THE TINY-YOLO'S v3 WORK (2)

	Google Cloud TPU	CPU Xeon(R) E5-1620
Recognition time (R=1280x720) per (s)	0.011	2.53
FPS (320 × 240)	36.1	7.3
Power Consumption (W)	200	90

The results from Tables I and II and Figure 7 show that the recognition speed on the MAIX AI is slower than a desktop GPUs. This can be explained by the fact that the platform is low on RAM. When the neural network is in operation, all of the RAM is filled. The results of the recognition time of a single image do not depend directly on the FPS in the video stream. This is because the image size for the tests does not match the size of the video stream frames. We can also notice from the tables the value of power consumption which is very low on the MAix AI platform in conjunction with other technologies.

Fig. 7. Results of detecting the sign: Prohibitory

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper describes the implementation of Tiny-YOLOv3 on the AIOT platform MAIX AI. The network trained to recognize and classify traffic signs shows good results and

verifies the ability to use Tiny-YOLOv3 for real-time image processing on an AIOT platform. While the CNN inference on the MAIX AI accelerator is pretty slow, it shows good quality traffic sign recognition. We got 9:2 frames per second proving that our AIOT platform meets the real-time conditions. However, more powerful hardware such as Google Cloud TPU or NVIDIA GTX 1050ti is required for good accuracy. With a low consumption of up to 0.5 watts and a fairly affordable price, such an AIOT platform in combination with Tiny-YOLOv3 is a good choice for advanced driver assistance systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Stallkamp, M. Schlipsing, J. Salmen, and C. Igel, "Man vs. computer: Benchmarking machine learning algorithms for traffic sign recognition," *Neural networks*, vol. 32, pp. 323–332, 2012.
- [2] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, and A. Courville, *Deep learning*. MIT press, 2016.
- [3] R. Girshick, J. Donahue, T. Darrell, and J. Malik, "Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2014, pp. 580–587.
- [4] M. Mathias, R. Timofte, R. Benenson, and L. Van Gool, "Traffic sign recognition—how far are we from the solution?" in *The 2013 international joint conference on Neural networks (IJCNN)*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 1–8.
- [5] J. Li and Z. Wang, "Real-time traffic sign recognition based on efficient cnns in the wild," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 975–984, 2018.
- [6] V. Khryashchev, A. Ostrovskaya, V. Pavlov, and A. Semenov, "Optimization of convolutional neural network for object recognition on satellite images," in *2018 Systems of Signal Synchronization, Generating and Processing in Telecommunications (SYNCHROINFO)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–5.
- [7] A. Baldominos, Y. Saez, and P. Isasi, "Evolutionary convolutional neural networks: An application to handwriting recognition," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 283, pp. 38–52, 2018.
- [8] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, and A. Farhadi, "You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2016, pp. 779–788.
- [9] S. P. Rajendran, L. Shine, R. Pradeep, and S. Vijayaraghavan, "Real-time traffic sign recognition using yolov3 based detector," in *2019 10th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [10] J. Redmon and A. Farhadi, "Yolo9000: better, faster, stronger," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2017, pp. 7263–7271.
- [11] M. Ju, H. Luo, Z. Wang, B. Hui, and Z. Chang, "The application of improved yolo v3 in multi-scale target detection," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 18, p. 3775, 2019.
- [12] <https://www.seedstudio.com/sipeed/>, 2008, [Online; accessed 2021].
- [13] R. Timofte, K. Zimmermann, and L. Van Gool, "Multi-view traffic sign detection, recognition, and 3d localisation," *Machine vision and applications*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 633–647, 2014.